

Mulch sowing in organic agriculture

Problem

Ploughing provides many advantages, such as weed control and enhanced mineralization of nutrients, but can also cause negative effects, especially when water or nutrients are restricted. Specifically, ploughing destroys the soil aggregate and capillary structure, increases the mineralisation of soil organic matter and causes soil compaction, all impacting soil health and functions. It also decreases load bearing capacity and may negatively influence water, gas and nutrient cycles.

Solution

Mulch sowing is a method of reduced soil tillage, based on sowing a main crop into the crop residues of the previous crop or catch crop. The soil is loosened, but not turned, and only an upper, shallow layer is mixed thoroughly.

Benefits

The organic material remaining on the soil surface protects the soil from crusting/sealing and erosion. The decomposing organic matter in the upper soil layer enriches the soil with humus. The lack of soil in-version preserves the soil structure, improving soil environment and thus the bearing capacity and water retention of the soil, as well as increasing the earthworm population. Reduced-tillage methods also usually reduce costs, including those related to fossil fuel consumption, compared to ploughing.

Practical recommendation

- Supporting measures:
 - Selection of suitable crops (see below) that are less susceptible to weeds as well as high-growth, nitrogen-efficient varieties.
 - Ensure constant soil cover to suppress weeds.
 - Under-sowing to prevent late weed infestation (e.g. white or small red clover varieties or mixtures).
- Start with simple procedures, such as:
 - Winter grain legumes, cereals or oilseed rape after cereals, potatoes or other root vegetables.
 - Green manure/intermediate crop for forage after silage maize, potatoes or cereals. (e.g. vetch- oats-peas mixture, mustard, cereal-grain legumes mixtures).
- Equipment/Machinery Considerations:
 - Examples of suitable machines for reduced tillage are a cultivator with wing-shares (Fig.1) or overlapping swing shares (i.e. disc harrow) (Fig.2) and, for heavy clay soils, a stubble plough.
 - Working depth: at least 10cm deep to eliminate thistles and docks. Adjust machines to shallow working depth; a depth guidance may be needed.
 - Seed drill: if organic matter or soil surface is well decomposed or not too abundant (after potatoes, cereals, or silage maize) use normal sowing machinery. If more abundant, rather use a disc drill.

Applicability box

Theme

Reduced soil tillage, mulch sowing with less harvest residues

Agronomic conditions

Temperate climate, Switzerland

Application time

Whole year

Required time

No additional time acquired

Period of impact

Following crop

Equipment

Cultivator, disc harrow, seed drill

Best in

After potatoes, maize and cereals

Fig. 1: Cultivator (H.Dierauer, FiBL)

- Preparing the seedbed:
 - After silage maize and potatoes, preparing the seedbed and sowing can take place immediately.
 - After cereals, wait until volunteer grains have germinated.
 - After green manure and corn, wait 10-14 days until organic matter has decomposed (or apply manure before tillage).
 - Use suitable tools, e.g., spring toothed harrow. Rotary or star disc harrow work under most conditions and do not tend to clog

Fig.2: Reduced tillage for mulch sowing, Disc harrow (FiBL, 2014)

- Make sure to produce enough soft soil for the seedbed with the primary soil tillage.
- Rolling the field after sowing facilitates germination and minimizes water evaporation.
- Reduced tillage after grassland is risky and only recommended for experienced farmers.

Use the comment section on the [SolACE discussion forum](#) to share your experiences with other farmers, advisors and scientists! If you have any questions concerning the method, please contact the first author of the practice abstract by e-mail.

Further information

Videos

- [Regulierung von Wurzelunkräutern bei der Stoppelbearbeitung mit Schälplflug oder Grubber](#) (English sub.)
- [Direkt- und Streifenfrässaat beim Biomais](#) (German)
- [Stickstoffnachlieferung aus Untersaaten und Beisaaten](#) (German)
- [Reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung mit Schälplflug - Maschinenvorführung August 2013](#) (English sub.)

Further reading

- Dierauer H., Gelencser T. 2019. Practice abstract "[Undersowing in cereals](#)". FiBL.
- Dierauer H. et al. 2014. "[Reduzierte Bodenbearbeitung – Umsetzung im Biologischen Landbau](#)", FiBL.
- Berner A. et al. 2016. Basic guide "The Basics of Soil fertility". FiBL & Organic Research Centre.

Weblinks

- [Soil tillage](#) in bioaktuell.ch (German/French)
- [Reduced tillage](#) on Ökologieundlandbau.de (German)

About this practice abstract and SolACE

Publisher: Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL
Ackerstrasse 113, Postfach 219, CH-5070 Frick
Phone +41 62 865 72 72, info.suisse@fibl.org, www.fibl.org

Authors: Matthias Klaiss, FiBL

Contact: matthias.klaiss@fibl.org

Permalink: zenodo.org/record/5211681

This practice abstract was elaborated in the SolACE project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. It was tested in field trials in Switzerland.

SolACE: The project is running from May 2017 to April 2022. The goal of SolACE (Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use) is to help European agriculture face major challenges, notably increased rainfall variability and reduced use of N and P fertilizers

Project website: www.solace-eu.net

© 2021

The project SolACE - "Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use" is supported by the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 727247, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 17.00094. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the EC and the Swiss government. Neither the European Commission/SERI nor any person acting behalf of the Commission/SERI is responsible for the use which might be made of the information provided on this practice abstract.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727247 (SolACE)

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI